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Effects Of Token Economy On The Management Of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Among Children In Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of token economy on the management of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder among children in schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental design involving pre-test and post-test design and control group design was adopted consisting of 30 primary 5 pupils from 3 public primary schools purposively drawn using simple random sampling. The participants were assigned into three groups; one treatment groups of token economy (TE) and one no-treatment control group. The Attention Deficit Checklist (ASC) was developed and used by the researcher for the study and comprised 18 items that assessed inattentiveness and hyperactivity/impulsive subtypes of ADHD presented on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Very often (4), Often (3), Sometimes (2) and Never (1). The checklist was validated by education experts and the reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained using the test-retest reliability method. Three research questions were answered with corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Data was collected and analysed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The findings revealed that both Token economy (Mean deviation = -27.90; $P = 000 < 0.05$) was effective in the reduction of ADHD symptoms among primary 5 pupils and this reduction was found to be statistically significant. Additionally, token economy (mean difference = -30.00, -23.00; $P = .956 > 0.05$) had more effect in male pupils than female pupils although these differences were not statistically significant. Furthermore, at follow-up, there was evidenced significant treatment retention among the treatment groups and an increase in symptom performance among the control group. Based on these findings, it is recommended that educators should be properly trained on the effective use of token economy procedures to reduce the symptoms of ADHD. Also, awareness towards early detection and intervention should be intensified to prevent deterioration.

Keywords: token economy, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, children

INTRODUCTION

The process of growth in human beings comprises the psychological, biological and emotional changes that happen from birth to childhood, to adolescence and to adulthood at maturity. This presents a predictable sequence of events. In children, this process involves a course that is peculiar to each child. This implies that growth sequence in children does not occur at the same rate although each stage is influenced by the experiences of the preceding stage. Developmental changes are influenced by genetics and other prenatal and environmental factors. In other words, they are changes that arise from learning

and environmental circumstances, or from genetically regulated processes called maturation (Toga, et al. 2006), but it most often results from an interplay between the two.

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by continuous lack of attention or concern, impulsive behaviour and decision-making, and inability to plan and organize and is first noticeable in early childhood (Goldstein & DeVries, 2017). It is said to be a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that interferes with functioning or development, as characterized by inattention and/or hyperactivity and impulsivity (American Psychirtric Association, 2013). The world health organization through the 11th edition of the International Classification of Diseases provided some distinction in their definition of ADHD. They referred to it as being characterized by a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that is more frequent and severe than typically observed in individuals at a comparable level of development. It usually manifests in early childhood and causes significant impairment in personal, family, social, educational, occupational, or other important areas of functioning (World Health Organization, 2024). Similarly, Nwankwo (2013) refers to ADHD as a disorder which features frequent restlessness in children with presenting record of low performance in activities for which diligence is required while exhibiting mood variations. This definition agrees with the practical meaning alluded to it by the National Institute of Mental Health (2021) based on the symptoms and impact. They defined it as a disorder that makes it difficult for a person to pay attention and control impulsive behaviours. It may also cause the person to be restless and almost constantly active. Symptoms include inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity.

The definitions above imply that ADHD is a neurodevelopment disorder that begins manifestation from childhood and can last all through the lifetime of the individual. The person(s) so diagnosed manifest restlessness, difficulty concentrating on tasks, inability to control oneself in response to certain stimuli. For a diagnosis to be made, these manifestations of inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity must be persistent and be present for about 6 months and counting and must be seen to interfere with normal functioning of the individual.

Children oftentimes struggle to pay attention, listen and follow instructions, sit and wait their turns. This does not always mean ADHD. In children with ADHD the struggle is usually harder. They manifest inattentiveness by being easily distracted, having trouble focusing their attention, concentrating, and staying on task. They may not listen well to directions, may miss important details, and may not finish what they start. They may daydream or dawdle too much. They may seem absent-minded or forgetful, and lose track of their things. Furthermore, they exhibit hyperactivity by being fidgety, restless, and easily bored. They may have trouble sitting still, or staying quiet when needed. They may rush through things and make careless mistakes. They may climb, jump, or roughhouse when they shouldn't. Unintentionally, they may act in ways that disrupt others. For impulsivity, these children act too quickly before thinking. They often interrupt, might push or grab, and find it hard to wait. They may do things without asking for permission, take things that aren't theirs, or act in ways that are risky. They may have emotional reactions that seem too intense for the situation (Hasan, 2022).

ADHD is considered a common disorder of childhood; however, this condition has been seen to persist in adulthood. Researchers have been able to establish the prevalence of ADHD hence regarding it as a global concern affecting people of different ages, races and genders. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), ADHD affects around 5% of children and 2.5% of adults worldwide. That means there are millions of people living with ADHD around the world (ABA, 2023). Studies in Nigeria have also confirmed the prevalence of ADHD in Nigeria. Adewuya and Famuyiwa (2007) in a survey found that 8.7% of Nigerian students aged 7 to 12 had ADHD. Their investigation also found that the prevalence of attention-deficit subtypes was determined to be 4.9%, hyperactivity/impulsivity subtype 1.2%, and hyperactivity and attention deficit subtype 2.6%.

Through the times in the diagnosis and study of ADHD, it is said that this disorder was originally known as hyperkinetic reaction of childhood and became recognized formally as a disorder in the 1960s by the American Psychiartric Association (APA). Later on, in the 1980s the name "attention deficit disorder with

or without hyperactivity” was given to the diagnosis (Holland, 2021). The progression from being known as hyperkinetic disease to ADHD began with German Doctors, Franz Kramer and Hans Pallow in 1932. They observed children who couldn't stay still, had difficulty staying still, and had problems getting along with other kids. This condition they noted started in children as young as 3 or 4 years and peaked at age 6. By 7, their restlessness became less intense and most got better as they got older hence, they called the condition hyperkinetic disease.

As a recognized condition, the causes remain a subject of discussion as there is no consensus among researchers as to what the causes may be. However, etiological explanations that underlie ADHD are grouped into two as biological and environmental. The biological includes heredity and the effect of brain structure on the neuropsychology, whereas the environmental factors include issues encountered during and after birth delivery, exposure to environmental toxins, parenting and diet (Singh, et al. 2015). In the development of ADHD, genetic predisposition is said to be a crucial factor. Family and twin research consistently indicate elevated rates of inheritability, estimated to be approximately 70-80% (Faraone & Larsson, 2019) (Wong, 2022). Particular genes linked are those related to the dopaminergic system, such as DRD4 (dopamine receptor D4) and DAT1 (dopamine transporter gene). Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have found multiple genetic regions linked to ADHD, underscoring its polygenic traits. (Wong, 2022). Research using brain scans and measurements of brain activity indicates that ADHD is linked to differences in brain structure and function. The prefrontal cortex, basal ganglia, and cerebellum are all crucial for executive functions and behavioural regulation, and these areas are impacted. Functional MRI studies frequently demonstrate decreased activity in the prefrontal cortex and irregularities in front striatal circuits, this provides a basis for the executive dysfunction theory (Faraone & Larsson, 2019). The disruption of neurotransmitters, dopamine and norepinephrine in particular, plays a key role in the pathophysiology of ADHD. Irregular dopamine signals impact cognitive functions like focus and processing rewards, which are found to be deficient in individuals with ADHD (NIMH, 2023). Environmental influences, especially those impacting early brain growth, also play a role in ADHD. Exposure to tobacco smoke, alcohol, and illicit drugs during pregnancy raises the likelihood of developing ADHD. Additional factors consist of infants being born with a low weight, being premature, and experiencing complications throughout the pregnancy and delivery. Factors occurring after birth, like lead exposure, brain injuries, and social stress, can also impact the progression and intensity of ADHD symptoms (Wong, 2022).

Several variables may contribute to the occurrence and detection of ADHD in Nigerian children: According to global data, genetic predisposition plays an important role in the development of ADHD. Children with a family history of ADHD face an increased risk.

ADHD management involves a multifaceted approach that includes behavioural therapy, pharmaceutical treatment, educational intervention and support measures. Effective management is aimed at reducing symptoms, improving function and improving the quality of life of individuals with ADHD. This implies that Pharmacotherapy and behavioural therapy are considered useful in treating attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in children, adolescents, and adults. Medically, stimulants such as Methylphenidate (Ritalin, Concerta), Amphetamine-based stimulants (Adderall, Vyvanse) are administered with the aim of quickly reducing the core symptoms of ADHD (inattention, hyperactivity, impulsivity) in about 70-80% of children. Also, non-stimulant medications such as Atomoxetine (Strattera), Guanfacine (Intuniv), Clonidine (Kapvay). These are considered Suitable for children who do not respond to stimulants or have contraindications and they have lower risk of misuse (Owens, et al., 2011). The use of medications is considered the standard of medical care for the symptoms of ADHD because they are efficacious and cost-effective when optimal dosing is achieved, since the patient usually manages treatment independently, requiring minimal physician input in the months and years after successful titration. On the other hand, Studies have shown evidence of benefits of behavioural therapy distinct from those of pharmacotherapy. Behavioural treatment involves the application of behavioural modification techniques such as token economies, and reward systems with the aim of helping the

children develop skills to control impulsive behaviours, increase attention, and improve academic performance in addition to teaching parents strategies to manage their child's behaviour, improves parent-child interactions, and reduces stress within the family (CDC, 2024). The American Academy of Pediatrics however posits that commencing ADHD treatment with behavioural therapy is cost effective over time than the use of medicine. They therefore recommend behavioural therapy as the first line for children ages 4 to 5. According to the guidelines, they have been shown to produce better overall results (Owens, et al., 2011). However, combining behavioural and medical treatments can more effectively manage ADHD symptoms than either approach alone. Medication can help children focus better in school, while behavioural interventions teach them skills to sustain this focus and improve their academic performance. Furthermore, this approach addresses multiple aspects of a child's life, including home, school, and social settings. Behavioural strategies can help improve family dynamics, while medication can reduce disruptive behaviours that interfere with learning and relationships. In other words, while medication can play a crucial role in managing the core symptoms of ADHD, behavioural interventions should be the first-line treatment for children. Behavioural therapy equips children with essential skills and strategies that support their development and overall well-being. When combined with medication, this holistic approach offers a balanced and effective strategy for managing ADHD, leading to better outcomes in various aspects of a child's life. This present study is concerned with the effects of the behavioural therapy technique in the management of ADHD among school children specifically token economy which is operant conditioning principles under behaviour modification strategies.

Behaviour modification is a therapeutic approach that seeks to change undesirable behaviours through the application of principles derived from operant conditioning and other learning theories. According to the American Psychological Association (2023), behaviour modification involves the systematic application of learning principles and techniques to assess and improve individuals' covert and overt behaviours in order to enhance their daily functioning (APA, 2023). This definition emphasizes the systematic and principled application of learning techniques to improve both observable and internal behaviours. It has also been defined as a type of treatment that deals with the investigation of behaviour, identification of undesirable or unacceptable responses, and then dealing with them by introducing relevant treatment such as reinforcement or punishment to alter them (Akinade, 2012). This definition is of the view that behaviour modification is a means of changing weak or excess behaviour using learning theories. Similarly, Nwankwo (2017) views behaviour modification as the changing of undesirable behaviour to desirable ones and increasing or enhancing the performance of desirable ones through the use of psychological principles and techniques specifically those of learning in a systematic and scientific way and the outcomes of the application of these psychological principles can be assessed and evaluated. This presents a robust definition that points out the key aspects of behaviour. Nwankwo (2017) from the definition believed that behaviour modification focuses on changing undesirable behaviours into acceptable ones and increasing desired behaviour that have insufficient performance. Put differently, behaviour modification involves the use of empirically based techniques and principles from learning theories to change undesirable behaviours. This therapeutic approach typically employs positive and negative reinforcement, punishment, extinction, and other behaviour change strategies to promote adaptive behaviours and reduce maladaptive ones. The concept of behaviour modification can therefore be understood as a structured, systematic, and evidence-based method to enhance an individual's behaviour and overall functioning. The behaviour modification techniques examined in the present study is, token economy. As such there is need to provide an overview of what they mean and are about in this introduction.

A token economy is a reinforcement system in which conditioned reinforcers called tokens are delivered to people for desirable behaviours: the tokens are later exchanged for backup reinforcers (Miltenberger, 2016). It is a procedure that requires the provision of conditioned reinforcers to clients by a therapist when a stipulated desired behaviour is achieved or performed (Nwankwo, 2017). The conditioned reinforces so indicated differs from the usual reinforcers like praises and material gifts that are applicable

in the direct reinforcement procedures. The conditioned reinforcers include award of points, tickets or symbols exchanged for the other material reinforces like books, pens, eraser which had been earlier agreed upon by the therapist and the client. This is aimed at increasing the frequency of occurrence of an acceptable behaviour that are not often performed as well as reduce the rate of occurrence of undesirable behaviour. This technique is applied in a structured treatment environment or educational setting (Miltenberger, 2016). Therefore, it is potentiated to be effective in managing the behaviour of children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. From the foregoing and based on the fact that attention deficit hyperactivity disorder specifies behaviours that are undesirable and not acceptable in home and school settings, it is therefore presumed that token economy may be effective in managing this disorder among school children.

Childhood is a period of several physical developments and activities. Some children manifest varying levels of inattention or hyperactivity that sometimes fizzles out as growth progresses into adulthood. As such when a child becomes diagnosed with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, it presents serious concerns for all involved. In as much as ADHD as a disorder has been described decades before now, its prevalence has in recent times been amplified. Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a prevalent neurodevelopmental disorder affecting children worldwide. With symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, ADHD can significantly impair a child's academic performance, social interactions, and overall quality of life. As an educator and the parent of a child diagnosed with ADHD, the researcher has personally witnessed the profound challenges and disruptions this condition can cause in a child's educational journey and daily functioning. Initially, the realization that the researcher's child manifested ADHD symptoms turned the world of this researcher upside down. The constant energy of the 7-year-old, his impulsivity and distractibility made everyday tasks feel like battles. He would often be restless and has difficulty focusing on specific tasks. Doing homework from school is a daily struggle and takes hours to complete owing to frequent distractions. Consequently, the boy struggles with missed assignments, difficulty maintaining friendships, feeling isolated, anxiety and meltdowns. The researcher also notes that these sentiments have been echoed by the parents of the children who manifest the symptoms of ADHD encountered in the course of working as an educator and a guidance counsellor.

The researcher's personal experience with this disorder highlights the critical need for effective management strategies that can be readily implemented at home and school settings. Current treatments for ADHD often include a combination of pharmacological interventions and behavioural therapies. While medications can provide symptomatic relief, they do not address the underlying behavioural issues and can have side effects that concern many parents and educators. Behavioural modification techniques such as token economy on the other hand, offer a non-pharmacological approach to managing ADHD, focusing on altering environmental factors and reinforcing positive behaviours to reduce symptoms and improve functioning. Despite the availability of various treatment options, there is a significant gap in the consistent and effective implementation of behaviour modification techniques in school settings. Many schools lack the resources, training, and support to effectively employ these strategies, leading to inconsistent results and continued challenges for children with ADHD. Additionally, the individual experiences of parents and children are often underrepresented in the research, resulting in a lack of personalized and practical solutions that can be adapted to diverse educational environments.

Despite there being abundant literature on the concept of ADHD, there is however limited published empirical works done in Nigeria with respect to the subject matter. These concerns form the persuasion of this researcher of the need to examine the effects of the token economy procedure in an educational setting involving school children which takes into consideration the effects of these procedures at follow-up.

Therefore, based on these gaps identified by the researcher, the problem of this study in question form is thus: what are the effects of token economy on the management of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder among school children in Rivers State?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of token economy in managing Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) among school children in Port Harcourt, Rivers state Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were to;

1. Investigate the effect of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, rivers state Nigeria.
2. Compare the mean difference of Token Economy (TE) group on the management of ADHD based on gender among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, rivers state Nigeria.
3. Determine the retention difference of token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers state.

Research Questions

To guide this study, the following research questions was answered:

1. What is the effect of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State?
2. What is the mean difference of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD based on gender among school children in Rivers State?
3. What is the retention difference of token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to further guide the study:

1. There is no significant mean difference between token economy and the control groups effects on ADHD management among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, rivers state Nigeria.
2. There is no significant mean difference between male and female respondent of Token Economy (TE) group on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the retention score of the respondent in the token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design involving pre-test and post-test design and control group design. A pretreatment measurement of the dependent variables was done to further confirm equivalence of the control and experimental groups. Then treatments which are the independent variables were administered on the experimental groups followed by a post-test measurement of the dependent variable from all groups which were administered after an interval of 6 weeks. There was a follow-up after 2 weeks for further comparison and assessment.

The target population for the study consisted of 28,304 primary 5 pupils in all the 36 public primary schools in Obio Akpor LGA of Rivers state. Simple random and purposive sampling was used to draw a sample of 20 participants that constituted the subjects for the study. This was achieved by selecting 3 public schools at random through balloting from the list of public primary schools in Obio Akpor LGA. After this was done, the researcher then administered the instrument which is the Attention Deficit Checklist (ASC) to the primary 5 pupils to purposively determine the participants for the study. This implies that the subjects that got a mean score of 37 and above were potential participants. For uniformity, economy of resources and control, the researcher further selected at random final participants for the study which was 20 from each of the 2 chosen schools and an even distribution between boys and girls (7 boys and 3 girls from each of the schools). The instrument that was used to collect data for this study was the Attention Deficit Symptoms checklist (ASC).

In order to ensure face and content validities, the researcher gave copies of the instrument to the researcher’s supervisors, one other expert in educational psychology and one measurement and evaluation expert who were requested to vet the instrument for clarity and eschew ambiguity. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using the test-retest reliability method. The obtained scores were then correlated to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.73 (See Appendix II). The researcher obtained informed consent from the authorities of the different schools that their pupils participated in this study.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the analysis of covariate (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Prior to the administration of the treatments as the case may be, ADHD was diagnosed in the children. To do this, the researcher and the teachers had to ascertain that the behaviours performed by the children were inappropriate for their ages, and that these behaviours interfered with their school work while persisting for six months (American Psychiatric Association APA, 2013). The essence of proper diagnosis ensured that the children who participated in the study have these symptoms of ADHD and were not being extra playful or immature. Therefore, the ASC scale was administered through the teachers who filled them out for the children. For the determination of ADHD through the instrument, a score of 37 and above was set. The copies of the instrument that returned with score 37 and above were included as part of the study and lower scores dismissed. The identified children for the periods of the sessions were converged in a classroom for this investigation.

One treatment group and one no treatment control group were involved in this study. The different groups were Token economy group (TE) and Control group (C). Subjects from each of the two identified schools were assigned to a specific group, that is to say that all participants in school 1 were assigned to the same experimental group and so it was for the other school and control group. This enabled ease of instruction, treatment and data collection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the effect of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation Analysis of children Pre-test and Post-test Scores of the Experimental Group 1 (token economy) and the Control Group

Group	Pre-Test Score		Post-Test Score		Mean Difference	
	N	\bar{x}	Sd	\bar{x}		Sd
Experimental Group 1- Token Economy	10	59.30	7.80	31.40	3.72	-27.90
Non treatment group - Control	10	60.10	5.21	60.50	5.38	0.40

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviation of children in the token economy and those in the control. The children in the token economy group had a pre-test mean score of 59.30 with a standard deviation of 7.80 while their post-test mean score is 31.40 with a standard deviation of 3.72. In addition, children in token economy had a mean difference (MD) of -27.90 and children in the control group had a pre-test mean score of 60.10 with a standard deviation of 5.21 while their post-test mean score is 60.50 with a standard deviation of 5.38 while a mean difference of 0.4. The difference in mean between the pre-test mean score and post-test scores for both groups (TE; -27.90 and Control; 0.4) implies that token economy as a management technique of ADHD is effective when compared to the no-treatment group.

Research Question 2: *What is the mean difference of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State based on gender?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation analysis of Token Economy (TE) on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers state based on gender.

Group	Strategy	Gender	N	Pre test		Post Test		Mean gain
				Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental 1	Token economy	Male	7	63.29	5.31	33.29	2.56	-30.00
		Female	3	50.00	2.00	27.00	1.00	-23.00

Results in Table 2 showed that male children exposed to token economy technique obtained a pretest score of 63.29 with a standard deviation of 5.31 while their post test score was 33.29 with a standard deviation of 2.56 with a mean difference of -30.00. On the other hand, the female children exposed to token economy technique obtained a pretest score of 50.00 with a standard deviation of 2.00 while their post test score was 27.00 with a standard deviation of 1.00 with a mean difference of -23.00 from the obtained mean difference, it was however deduced that the male children exposed to token economy had a higher mean reduction score over their female counterparts. This implies that token economy (TE) technique was more effective on the male school children than the female school children in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the retention difference of token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State?*

Table 4.7: Mean and Standard deviation Analysis of the three group Post-test and Retention Scores of token economy, response cost and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers State

Group	Post-Test Score			Retention-Test Score		Mean Difference
	N	\bar{x}	Sd	\bar{x}	Sd	
Experimental Group 1- token economy (TE)	10	31.40	3.72	28.40	4.12	-3.00
Non treatment group - Control	10	60.50	5.38	62.20	6.43	1.70

Table 3 shows the retention difference of token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in Rivers state. The children in the token economy group had a post-test mean score of 31.40 with a standard deviation of 3.72 and a retention score of 28.40 with a standard deviation of 4.12. Consequently, children in token economy had a mean difference (MD) of -3.00. While, children in the control group had a post-test mean score is 60.50 with a standard deviation of 5.38, and a retention score of 62.20 with a standard deviation of 6.43. In the case of their mean difference (MD), there was a slight increase of 0.40 giving a mean gain of 1.70. However, a closer look at the mean difference value for the token economy there was a further reduction in the mean differences of Token economy; (-3.0) indicating an improvement in managing Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) among school children in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant mean difference between token economy group and control group on ADHD management among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

To test the null hypothesis, analysis of covariance was employed. The results are presented in Table 4

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA on the mean difference between token economy and the control group on ADHD management among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4545.913 ^a	2	2272.956	529.050	.000	.984
Intercept	15.941	1	15.941	3.710	.071	.179
Pre.Test	311.863	1	311.863	72.589	.000	.810
Group	4072.881	1	4072.881	947.998	.000	.982
Error	73.037	17	4.296			
Total	46847.000	20				
Corrected Total	4618.950	19				

a. R Squared = .984 (Adjusted R Squared = .982)

Table 4 showed that the calculated F-value for token economy is 947.998 at degrees of freedom of 1 and 17 at $p < 0.00$. The calculated F-value was significant at $p < 0.00$ which is less than 0.05 level of probability ($F = 947.998$, $df = 1/17$, $p < 0.05$). Hypothesis two was therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant mean difference between token economy and the control group effects on ADHD management among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant mean difference between male and female respondent of Token Economy (TE) group on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

To test the null hypothesis, analysis of covariance was employed. The results are presented in Table 5

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA on the mean difference between male and female respondent of Token Economy (TE) group on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	122.200 ^a	2	61.100	194.438	.000	.982
Intercept	.676	1	.676	2.153	.186	.235
Pre.Test	39.229	1	39.229	124.837	.000	.947
Gender	.001	1	.001	.003	.956	.000
Error	2.200	7	.314			
Total	9984.000	10				
Corrected Total	124.400	9				

a. R Squared = .982 (Adjusted R Squared = .977)

Table 5 showed that the calculated F-value for male and female respondent of Token Economy (TE) group is 0.003 at degrees of freedom of 1 and 7 at $p = 0.956$. The calculated F-value was not significant at $p = 0.956$ which is greater than 0.05 level of probability ($F = 0.003$, $df = 1/7$, $p > 0.05$). Hypothesis five was therefore accepted. This implies that there is no significant mean difference between male and female respondent of Token Economy (TE) group on ADHD management among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the retention score of the respondent in the token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

A two-way analysis of covariance was used to test the null hypothesis. The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 4.14: Summary of ANCOVA on the retention score of the respondent in the token economy and control groups on the management of ADHD among school children in selected schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Source	Type II Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7782.858 ^a	3	2594.286	177.531	.000	.953
Intercept	42.750	1	42.750	2.925	.099	.101
Pre.Test	255.658	1	255.658	17.495	.000	.402
Group	7668.079	2	3834.039	262.369	.000	.953
Error	379.942	26	14.613			
Total	55684.000	30				
Corrected Total	8162.800	29				

a. R Squared = .953 (Adjusted R Squared = .948)

Table 6 showed that the calculated F-value for the group retention is 262.369 at degrees of freedom of 2 and 26 and it is significant at 0.000 probability level which is lesser than 0.05 level of probability (F= 262.369, df =2/26, p>0.05). Hypothesis three was therefore rejected. This therefore indicated that there is a significant difference in the retention score on the respondent on the management of ADHD among school children using token economy and the control group.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This theme addresses research questions one and two and hypotheses one and two of this study. The results here revealed that Children exposed to the token economy had a reduction in Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) than their counterparts in the non-treatment group (control), which implies that token economy (TE) has an effect on the management of Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). However, this effect was also statistically significant. Furthermore, the mean reduction score of male and female children token economy group differed in favour of the male children. In addition, the difference in mean reduction between male and female children in the token economy group on further statistical test was found to be significant. This result however differs from the findings of Murray, et al.(2021) who found that girls with ADHD responded well to token economies. This they attributed to their tendency to comply with structured reinforcement systems.

Result for research question and hypothesis three above showed that there was a further reduction in the retention score of Token economy; (-3.0) indicating a long-term improvement (retention) in managing Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) among school children in Rivers State. When this result was further subjected to hypothetical testing, there was a statistically significant difference in the retention effect of the token economy in the management of Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). This obtained result is similar to the submission of Pfiffner et al. (2016) whose study indicated a sustained improvement in both behaviour and academic performance, suggesting that token economies and response cost can have lasting positive effects on children with ADHD.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that token economy (TE) is effective in managing attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among school children in Rivers State, Nigeria. Token economy significantly reduce ADHD symptoms compared to non-treatment control groups. Additionally, while token economy is effective across genders, male students show a more pronounced improvement. Token economy is effective where management of ADHD is concerned. It is also important to note that the symptoms of ADHD may increase if no intervention is given to children.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation are made:

1. Adoption of token economy in schools: Schools in Rivers State should integrate token economy and response cost techniques into behaviour management programs to support children with ADHD effectively.
2. Customize interventions based on gender: since token economy show more effectiveness in male students, gender-sensitive approaches should be developed to enhance effectiveness for female students.
4. Training of teachers on behaviour management strategies: Educators should receive training on implementing token economy techniques to manage ADHD behaviours effectively in the classroom.
5. Develop ADHD support programs in schools: Schools should establish structured ADHD intervention programs incorporating both token economy techniques to provide continuous support.

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